

DIRECT APPLICATION OF THE CONSTITUTION AS AN IMPORTANT GUARANTEE OF HUMAN RIGHTS

Bobojonov Javoxir Islom oqli

Lecturer, Department of Constitutional Law, Tashkent
State University of Law E-mail: bobojavohir06@gmail.com
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16949808>

Abstract. The article analyzes the principle of the direct application of the Constitution as an important guarantee of human rights. First of all, it highlights that Article 15 of the newly revised Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan explicitly enshrines this provision and elaborates on its practical significance. It is substantiated that the direct application of constitutional norms in the activities of state bodies and officials serves as a foundation for building a democratic state governed by the rule of law. Referring to international experience, particularly the Basic Law of Germany and the decisions of the U.S. Supreme Court, the author emphasizes that Uzbekistan's constitutional reforms are in harmony with international democratic standards. On the basis of presidential decrees, the Plenum decision of the Supreme Court, and reports of the Constitutional Court, it is demonstrated that this principle is being widely applied in practice. In particular, it is shown that the direct application of constitutional norms in judicial practice has increased significantly.

Keywords: Constitution, basic law, rule of law, democracy, normative legal act, direct application, judicial practice, obligation, duty.

Introduction

One of the key features of a democratic state governed by the rule of law is that the adopted normative legal acts serve to ensure human rights and freedoms as well as the well-being of society. Most importantly, such acts should not remain merely on paper, but must turn into rules that are strictly observed by state bodies and their officials, and that serve as a guiding principle in practical activities.

In particular, compliance with and practical application of the Constitution — the supreme normative legal act of the state — must be regarded as the primary duty and responsibility of every state body and official. Indeed, in a society where the Constitution is respected and its provisions are duly observed, the rule of law is inevitably established.

Results

An important democratic provision has been incorporated into Article 15 of the newly revised Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan: "The Constitution

of the Republic of Uzbekistan shall have supreme legal force throughout the entire territory of the country and shall be applied directly” [1].

It is known that in the 1992 Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan [2], the principle of direct application was not explicitly enshrined. Therefore, the implementation of constitutional norms in practice was often carried out through other normative legal acts. In the new edition, however, this provision has been directly codified, thereby further strengthening the legal force of the Basic Law.

As President Shavkat Mirmonovich Mirziyoyev emphasized in his congratulatory address on the occasion of the 31st anniversary of the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan: “We must move towards the practice of applying the Constitution directly and immediately in all spheres of public life. Only then will our people deeply feel the vital power and impact of our Basic Law. In this regard, practical measures will be taken to introduce the direct application of constitutional norms in the activities of all state bodies, including the courts” [3].

Turning to international experience, the Basic Law of Germany also explicitly establishes the direct application of the Constitution, and courts are obliged to apply these norms directly in practice [4]. Similarly, the decisions of the U.S. Supreme Court recognize the provisions of the Constitution as directly applicable legal sources. This demonstrates that Uzbekistan’s new constitutional reform is consistent with international democratic standards [5].

Undoubtedly, the direct application of the Constitution does not occur automatically. In order to strengthen the role and significance of the Constitution in the activities of state bodies and to achieve its direct implementation, numerous measures have been taken and a number of important documents have been adopted.

On May 8, 2023, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted Decree No. PF-67 “On the First Priority Measures for the Implementation of the New Edition of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan.” This decree strictly established the following provisions: “Heads of state bodies and organizations are personally responsible for ensuring the timely implementation of measures related to the enforcement of the new edition of the Constitution; given that the new edition of the Constitution has supreme legal force, it shall be applied directly and unconditionally in the activities of state bodies and organizations, including courts and law enforcement agencies; refusal to apply the provisions of the new edition of the Constitution on the grounds of the absence of other

legislative acts necessary for its implementation, or due to the lack of amendments and additions to the legislation in accordance with the Constitution, is strictly prohibited” [6].

Undoubtedly, the establishment of such provisions became an important foundation for the practical application of Article 15 of the Constitution. This decree not only ensures the direct effect of constitutional norms, but also increases the responsibility of state bodies, making their activities more transparent and effective. Most importantly, this requirement has become a legal guarantee for the implementation of the principle of “individual — society — state” within the public administration system. From now on, every leader assumes personal responsibility for putting the Constitution into practice.

It is well known that the humanitarian and democratic norms of the Constitution are particularly essential in judicial practice. From this point of view, without adherence to the Constitution by the courts, its practical application cannot be fully realized. For this purpose, the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted the Resolution “On Certain Issues of the Direct Application of the Provisions of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the Administration of Justice.” This resolution marked a new stage in the practical application of constitutional norms by the courts. As emphasized in the Plenum’s decision, courts must assess the content of the law or other normative legal act regulating the relevant legal relations and apply the provisions of the Constitution directly as the supreme normative legal basis with binding legal force [7].

At the same time, this decision contributed to the formation of a unified approach in the practice of courts regarding the application of constitutional norms. Indeed, resolving legal issues in judicial decisions by directly relying on the provisions of the Constitution not only protects the rights and freedoms of citizens but also strengthens the supremacy of the Constitution within the entire legal system.

At this point, it is appropriate to elaborate on the concept of the direct application of the Constitution. The direct application of the Constitution means that state bodies and their officials, including courts, use constitutional provisions as a direct legal basis when making decisions. This also envisions that citizens themselves can directly rely on and exercise the rights and freedoms guaranteed by the Constitution. For example, ministries, local administrations, courts, the prosecutor’s office, internal affairs, and other institutions, when

adopting a decision on a particular matter, explicitly refer to the relevant provision of the Constitution.

Citizens, in turn, may rely on constitutional provisions in their daily lives to exercise their rights. For instance, Article 47 of the Constitution stipulates that no one may be deprived of housing without a court decision. If this requirement is violated, a citizen may invoke the constitutional guarantee to protect his or her rights.

As a result of the introduction of this rule, excuses such as “no relevant procedure has been developed” or “no order has been received from above” can no longer obstruct the enjoyment of constitutional rights. Consequently, the provisions of the Constitution are ensured to have direct effect, regardless of whether the procedure for their application is established in specific legislative acts.

This significant constitutional amendment soon began to be reflected in judicial practice. According to the 2024 report of the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the state of constitutional legality in the country, references to the Constitution and its articles were made in 73,242 criminal cases (4.8 times more compared to 2023), 25,083 civil cases (5.6 times more), 30,301 economic cases (13.6 times more), and 8,837 administrative cases (13 times more). The courts most frequently referred to Articles 26, 27, 28, 29, and 31 (criminal cases); Articles 15, 20, 26, 29, 31, 33, 41, 42, 46, 47, 55, 60, 62–68, 76–78, and 80 (civil cases); Articles 15, 16, 55, 65–68, 99, 134, and 138 (economic cases); and Articles 15, 20, 21, 29, 30, 40, 41, 46, 54, 55, 65–67, and 138 (administrative cases) [8].

Conclusion

The above information demonstrates that the direct application of the Constitution has begun to yield results not only in theory but also in practice. As a consequence, constitutional provisions are being increasingly applied as primary sources in judicial and legal practice, thereby contributing to the strengthening of the rule of law.

In conclusion, the direct application of the Constitution is one of the most important guarantees for building a democratic state governed by the rule of law. This principle plays an invaluable role in strengthening citizens’ trust in the state, as well as in enhancing legal awareness and legal culture within society. In the future, the full and unconditional application of constitutional norms in the activities of state bodies and officials, along with the expansion of legal

education and awareness among the population, will further increase the effectiveness of this principle.

References:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Konstititsiyasi. (2023) Qonunchilik ma'lumotlari milliy bazasi, 01.05.2023-y., 03/23/837/0241-son
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Konstititsiyasi. (1992) Qonun hujjatlari ma'lumotlari milliy bazasi, 06.03.2019-y., 03/19/527/2706-son, 05.09.2019-y., 03/19/563/3685-son; 09.02.2021-y., 03/21/670/0089-son, 09.02.2021-y., 03/21/671/0093-son
3. Shavkat Mirziyoyev: Konstitutsiyani to'g'ridan to'g'ri qo'llash amaliyotiga o'tishimiz zarur. <https://kun.uz/60279541>
4. Basic Law for the Federal Republic of Germany. https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/englisch_gg/englisch_gg.html
5. Marbury v. Madison, 5 U.S. (1 Cranch) 137 (1803). <https://supreme.justia.com/cases/federal/us/5/137/>
6. Yangi tahrirdagi O'zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasini amalga oshirish bo'yicha birinchi navbatdagi chora-tadbirlar to'g'risida O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 08.05.2023 yildagi PF-67-son farmoni. Qonunchilik ma'lumotlari milliy bazasi, 10.05.2023-y., 06/23/67/0269-son
7. Odil sudlovni amalga oshirishda O'zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasi normalarini to'g'ridan-to'g'ri qo'llashning ayrim masalalari to'g'risida O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy sudi Plenumining 23.06.2023 yildagi 16-son qarori. <https://lex.uz/docs/-6523654>
8. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyaviy sudining mamlakatdagi konstitutsiyaviy qonuniylikning holati to'g'risidagi axborotini tasdiqlash haqida O'zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyaviy sudining 06.12.2024 yildagi KSQ-4-son qarori. <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/-7251202>

